

CODEN [USA]: IAJPB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION BY RP HPLC METHOD
OF MOXIFLOXACIN AND LEVOFLOXACIN IN BULK AND
PHARMACEUTICAL FORMULATION****Medamoni Harish Yadav^{1*}, DR. Jagadeesh Babu, Dr. D. Varun.**¹ Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Sri Indu Institute of Pharmacy,
Sheriguda (V), Ibrahimpatnam, Telangana- 501510**Abstract:**

A simple, precise, and accurate reverse-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method was developed and validated for the simultaneous estimation of moxifloxacin and levofloxacin in bulk drug substances and pharmaceutical formulations. Chromatographic separation was achieved using a Symmetry ODS C18 column (4.6 mm × 150 mm, 5 μm particle size) maintained at 38°C, with a mobile phase comprising methanol and water in the ratio of 64:36 v/v. The elution was performed at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min, and detection was carried out at a wavelength of 220 nm using a Waters Alliance 2695 HPLC system coupled with a PDA Detector (996 model). The injection volume was 20 μl, and the total run time was 7.0 minutes. The method was validated according to ICH guidelines for parameters such as linearity, accuracy, precision, specificity, and robustness. The retention times of moxifloxacin and levofloxacin were well-resolved with no interference from formulation excipients, indicating the method's suitability for routine quality control. The developed method offers a reliable, efficient, and cost-effective approach for the simultaneous quantification of these two fluoroquinolone antibiotics in various pharmaceutical dosage forms.

Keywords: RP-HPLC, moxifloxacin, levofloxacin, Symmetry ODS C18 column, simultaneous estimation, validation, Waters Alliance 2695 HPLC.

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Please cite this article in press Medamoni Harish Yadav et al., Development And Validation By RP HPLC Method Of Moxifloxacin And Levofloxacin In Bulk And Pharmaceutical Formulation, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2026; 13(01).

1. INTRODUCTION:

Pharmaceutical Analysis is used to determining the qualitative and quantitative composition of material under study. Both these aspects are necessary to understand the sample material. Analytical chemistry is divided into two branches quantitative and qualitative. A qualitative analysis gives us the information about the nature of sample by knowing about the presence or absence of certain components. A quantitative analysis provides numerical information as to the relative amount of one or more of these components.

For analyzing the drug samples in bulk, pharmaceutical formulations and biological fluids, different analytical methods are routinely being used. In non-instrumental, the conventional and physicochemical property are use to analyze the sample. The instrumental methods of analysis are based upon the measurements of some physical property of substance using instrument to determine its chemical composition. The instrumental methods are simple, precise and reproducible as compared to classical methods. Therefore, analytical methods developed using sophisticated instruments such as spectrophotometer, HPLC, GC and HPTLC have wide applications in assuring the quality and quantity of raw materials and finished products.

Analytical chemistry is the branch of chemistry focused on the identification and quantification of chemical substances. It involves the use of various techniques and instruments to analyze the composition of materials, determine their molecular structure, and understand their properties. Analytical chemistry plays a vital role in many fields, including pharmaceuticals, environmental science, forensics, food safety, and materials science.

The field is typically divided into two main types of analysis:

1. **Qualitative analysis** – Determines what substances are present in a sample.
2. **Quantitative analysis** – Measures how much of a specific substance is present.

1. PRINCIPLE OF CHROMATOGRAPHY:

Adsorption Chromatography:

When the stationary phase is a solid and mobile phase is liquid or gaseous phase, it is called Adsorption Chromatography.

Examples: Thin layer chromatography,

Partition Chromatography:

When the stationary phase and mobile phase are liquid, it is called Partition Chromatography.

Example: Paper partition chromatography, Gas-liquid.

Phases of Chromatography

Normal Phase Chromatography:

In Normal Phase mode the stationary phase is polar and the mobile phase is non-polar in nature.

In this technique, non-polar compounds travel faster and are eluted first. This is because of the lower affinity between the non-polar compounds and the stationary phase. Polar compounds are retained for longer times because of their higher affinity with the stationary phase. These compounds, therefore take more times to elute. Normal phase mode of separation is therefore, not generally used for pharmaceutical applications because most of the drug molecules are polar in nature and hence take longer time to elute.

Reversed Phase Chromatography:

It is the most popular mode for analytical and preparative separations of compound of interest in chemical, biological, pharmaceutical, food and biomedical sciences. In this mode the stationary phase is non polar hydrophobic packing with octal or octa decyl functional group bonded to silica gel and the mobile phase is polar solvent. The polar compound gets eluted first in this mode and non-polar compounds are retained for longer time. As most of the drugs and pharmaceuticals are polar in nature, they are not retained for longer times and hence elute faster. The different columns used are Octa Decyl Silane (ODS) or C18, C8, C4, (in the order of increasing polarity of the stationary phase). An aqueous mobile phase allows the use of secondary solute chemical equilibrium (such as ionization control, ion suppression, ion pairing and complexation) to control retention and selectivity

Method Development:

Analytical method development and validation play important roles in the discovery development and manufacture of pharmaceuticals. These methods used to ensure the identity, purity, potency, & performance of drug products. There are many factors to consider when developing methods. The initially collect the information about the analyte's physicochemical properties (pKa, log P, solubility) and determining which mode of detection would be suitable for analysis (i.e., suitable wavelength in case of UV detection)¹.

The majority of the analytical development effort goes into validating a stability indicating HPLC-method. The goal of the HPLC-method is to try & separate quantify the main active drug, any reaction impurities, all available synthetic intermediates and any degradants. Steps involve in method development are:

1. Understand the physicochemical properties of drug molecule.
2. Set up HPLC conditions.
3. Preparation of sample solution for method development.
4. Method optimization.

5. Validation of method².**EXPERIMENTAL METHODS****INSTRUMENTS USED**

HPLC WATERS Alliance 2695 separation module, Software: Empower 2, 996 PDA detector.

pH meter Lab India

Weighing machine Sartorius

Volumetric flasks Borosil

Pipettes and Burettes Borosil

Beakers Borosil

Digital ultra sonicator Labman

CHEMICALS USED:

Levofloxacin Provided by Sura Pharma labs

Moxifloxacin Provided by Sura Pharma labs

Water and Methanol for HPLC LICHROSOLV (MERCK)

Acetonitrile for HPLC Merck

HPLC METHOD DEVELOPMENT:**TRAILS****Preparation of standard solution:**

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Levofloxacin and Moxifloxacin working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Methanol and sonicate to dissolve and removal of air completely and make volume up to the mark with the same Methanol.

Further pipette 0.6ml of Levofloxacin and 1ml of Moxifloxacin from the above stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Methanol.

Procedure:

Inject the samples by changing the chromatographic conditions and record the chromatograms, note the conditions of proper peak elution for performing validation parameters as per ICH guidelines.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**Trail 4: Optimized Chromatogram (Standard)**

Mobile phase : Methanol: Water (64:36% v/v)

Column : Symmetry ODS C18 (4.6mm×150mm) 5µm Particle Size

Flow rate : 1 ml/min

Wavelength : 220nm

Temperature = 38°C

Injection Volume : 20 µl

Run time : 7 minutes

Fig 7.4: Optimized Chromatogram (Standard)

Table:7.4 - peak results for optimized

S. No	Peak name	R _t	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP plate count
1	Levofloxacin	2.456	600122	112157		1.6	5215
2	Moxifloxacin	4.312	422042	51068	3.2	1.5	5648

Observation: From the above chromatogram it was observed that the Levofloxacin and Moxifloxacin peaks are well separated and they show proper retention time, resolution, peak tail and plate count. So it's optimized trial.

Optimized Chromatogram (Sample)**Figure:7.5 Optimized Chromatogram (Sample)****Table: 7.5 Optimized Chromatogram (Sample)**

S. No	Peak name	R _t	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP plate count
1	Levofloxacin	2.460	600123	112157		1.6	5011
2	Moxifloxacin	4.315	422041	51068	3.3	1.5	5947

Acceptance criteria:

- Resolution between two drugs must be not less than 2
- Theoretical plates must be not less than 2000
- Tailing factor must be not less than 0.9 and not more than 2.
- It was found from above data that all the system suitability parameters for developed method were within the limit.

VALIDATION**Blank:****Fig7.6: Chromatogram showing blank (mobile phase preparation)****System suitability:****Table:7.6 Results of system suitability for Levofloxacin**

S.no	Name	R _t	Area	Height	USP plate count	USP Tailing
1	Levofloxacin	2.459	602561	111160	5123	1.4
2	Levofloxacin	2.466	600543	53992	5023.2	1.4
3	Levofloxacin	2.472	601288	55420	5061.3	1.3
4	Levofloxacin	2.452	600776	112478	5147.3	1.6
5	Levofloxacin	2.450	600758	111779	5101.8	1.7
Mean			601185.2			
Std. Dev			816.3576			
% RSD			0.13			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2
- The %RSD obtained is within the limit, hence the method is suitable.

Table 7.7: Results of system suitability for Moxifloxacin

S.no	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP plate count	USP Tailing	USP Resolution
1	Moxifloxacin	4.322	422674	50988	5949	1.5	3.2
2	Moxifloxacin	4.323	424692	49813	5890.0	1.5	3.3
3	Moxifloxacin	4.342	421255	49826	5952.5	1.4	3.2
4	Moxifloxacin	4.300	415235	51804	5926.4	1.50	3.2
5	Moxifloxacin	4.295	416260	51274	5898.5	1.49	3.2
Mean			420023.2				
Std. Dev			724.7845				
% RSD			0.17				

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD for sample should be NMT 2
- The %RSD for the standard solution is below 1, which is within the limits hence method is precise.

SPECIFICITY

The ICH documents define specificity as the ability to assess unequivocally the analyte in the presence of components that may be expected to be present, such as impurities, degradation products, and matrix components. Analytical method was tested for specificity to measure accurately quantitative Levofloxacin and Moxifloxacin in drug product.

Assay (Standard):**Table 7.8 Peak results for assay standard**

S.no	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP plate count	Injection
1	Levofloxacin	2.456	600122	112157		1.5	5023	1
2	Moxifloxacin	4.312	420842	51068	3.3	1.4	5946	1
3	Levofloxacin	2.457	600205	112399		1.2	5149	2
4	Moxifloxacin	4.308	422034	51511	3.3	1.4	5848	2
5	Levofloxacin	2.456	600213	11201		1.5	5046	3
6	Moxifloxacin	4.312	420191	52014	3.2	1.5	5941	3

Assay (Sample):**Table 7.9 Peak results for Assay sample**

S.no	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP Resolution	USP Tailing	USP plate count	Injection
1	Levofloxacin	2.465	601812	110102		1.6	5028	1
2	Moxifloxacin	4.337	414764	49842	3.2	1.5	5949	1
3	Levofloxacin	2.474	600435	108333		1.6	5189	2
4	Moxifloxacin	4.356	418130	48360	3.3	1.5	5818	2
5	Levofloxacin	2.465	600212	112453		1.6	5061	3
6	Moxifloxacin	4.337	413645	48641	3.2	1.5	5812	3

%ASSAY =

$$\frac{\text{Sample area}}{\text{Standard area}} \times \frac{\text{Weight of standard}}{\text{Dilution of standard}} \times \frac{\text{Dilution of sample}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times \frac{\text{Purity}}{100} \times \frac{\text{Weight of tablet}}{\text{Label claim}} \times 100$$

The % purity of Levofloxacin and Moxifloxacin in pharmaceutical dosage form was found to be 99.9% and 98.2%

LINEARITY

CHROMATOGRAPHIC DATA FOR LINEARITY STUDY:

Levofloxacin:

Concentration µg/ml	Average Peak Area
20	215760
40	417001
60	600435
80	791969
100	974736

Figure 7.23 Calibration Graph for Levofloxacin

LINEARITY PLOT:

The plot of Concentration (x) versus the Average Peak Area (y) data of Levofloxacin is a straight line.

$$Y = mx + c$$

$$\text{Slope (m)} = 9693.9$$

$$\text{Intercept (c)} = 15288$$

$$\text{Correlation Coefficient (r)} = 0.999$$

VALIDATION CRITERIA: The response linearity is verified if the Correlation Coefficient is 0.99 or greater.

CONCLUSION: Correlation Coefficient (r) is 0.99, and the intercept is 15288. These values meet the validation criteria.

Moxifloxacin

Concentration µg/ml	Average Peak Area
60	309972
80	421045
100	532151
120	631671

140	711671
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Figure 7.24 Calibration graph for Moxifloxacin

LINEARITY PLOT:

The plot of Concentration (x) versus the Average Peak Area (y) data of Moxifloxacin is a straight line.

$$Y = mx + c$$

$$\text{Slope (m)} = 5166.7$$

$$\text{Intercept (c)} = 3862.2$$

$$\text{Correlation Coefficient (r)} = 0.998$$

VALIDATION CRITERIA: The response linearity is verified if the Correlation Coefficient is 0.99 or greater.

CONCLUSION: Correlation Coefficient (r) is 0.99, and the intercept is 3862.2. These values meet the validation criteria.

Precision:

The precision of an analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement (degree of scatter) between a series of measurements obtained from multiple sampling of the same homogeneous sample under the prescribed conditions.

REPEATABILITY

Obtained Five (5) replicates of 100% accuracy solution as per experimental conditions. Recorded the peak areas and calculated % RSD.

Table:7.10 Results of repeatability for Levofloxacin:

S.No	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP plate count	USP Tailing
1	Levofloxacin	2.453	603403	112688	5881.3	1.4
2	Levofloxacin	2.455	608107	113637	5844.1	1.3
3	Levofloxacin	2.453	607266	112849	5918.1	1.3
4	Levofloxacin	2.452	608776	112478	5847.3	1.4
5	Levofloxacin	2.450	609758	111779	5801.8	1.5
Mean			607462			
Std. Dev			2445.82			
% RSD			0.40			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD for sample should be NMT 2
- The %RSD for the standard solution is below 1, which is within the limits hence method is precise.

Table:7.11 Results of method precession for Moxifloxacin:

S.No	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP plate count	USP Tailing	USP Resolution
1	Moxifloxacin	4.289	429183	52411	5050.9	1.49	3.2
2	Moxifloxacin	4.309	416643	52475	5084.8	1.5	3.2
3	Moxifloxacin	4.306	424052	51841	5000.1	1.4	3.2
4	Moxifloxacin	4.300	425235	51804	5026.4	1.51	3.2
5	Moxifloxacin	4.295	416260	51274	5098.5	1.51	3.2
Mean			422274.6				
Std. Dev			5646.668				
% RSD			1.3				

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD for sample should be NMT 2
- The %RSD for the standard solution is below 1, which is within the limits hence method is precise.

Intermediate precision:**Day 1:****Table:7.12 Results of Intermediate precision for Levofloxacin**

S.No	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP plate count	USP Tailing
1	Levofloxacin	2.465	602386	111226	5075.9	1.5
2	Levofloxacin	2.472	608118	112497	5043.2	1.3
3	Levofloxacin	2.467	605566	110347	5029.9	1.5
4	Levofloxacin	2.466	608543	53992	5023.2	1.4
5	Levofloxacin	2.472	609288	55420	5061.3	1.4
6	Levofloxacin	3.424	607315	54154	5078.4	1.3
Mean			606869.3			
Std. Dev			2538.025			
% RSD			0.41			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2.

Table:7.13 Results of Intermediate precision for Moxifloxacin

S. No	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP plate count	USP Tailing	USP Resolution
1	Moxifloxacin	4.323	422252	50991	5886.2	1.6	3.2
2	Moxifloxacin	4.343	418090	50664	5947.5	1.5	3.2
3	Moxifloxacin	4.324	424361	50295	5907.8	1.55	3.2
4	Moxifloxacin	4.323	424692	49813	5890.0	1.50	3.2
5	Moxifloxacin	4.342	411255	49826	5852.5	1.49	3.2
6	Moxifloxacin	4.323	422252	50991	5756.8	1.50	3.2
Mean			420483.7				

Std. Dev			5096.974				
% RSD			1.2				

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of six different sample solutions should not more than 2
- The %RSD obtained is within the limit, hence the method is rugged.

Day 2:**Table:7.14 Results of Intermediate precision Day 2 for Levofloxacin**

S. No	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP plate count	USP Tailing
1	Levofloxacin	2.456	602581	112175	5013	1.7
2	Levofloxacin	2.457	600985	112422	5007	1.7
3	Levofloxacin	2.456	600145	114513	5198	1.8
4	Levofloxacin	2.459	600332	111580	5246	1.7
5	Levofloxacin	2.467	600566	110347	5096	1.8
6	Levofloxacin	2.459	600332	111580	5178	1.8
Mean			600823.5			
Std. Dev			908.2622			
% RSD			0.15			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2

Table:7.15 Results of Intermediate precision for Moxifloxacin

S. No	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP plate count	USP Tailing	USP Resolution
1	Moxifloxacin	4.312	425263	50936	5981	1.5	3.2
2	Moxifloxacin	4.308	427069	51400	5887	1.49	3.2
3	Moxifloxacin	4.312	424231	51236	5928	1.5	3.2
4	Moxifloxacin	4.322	423569	51084	5898	1.50	3.2
5	Moxifloxacin	4.324	414361	50295	5887	1.5	3.2
6	Moxifloxacin	4.322	413569	51084	5940	1.5	3.2
Mean			421343.7				
Std. Dev			5841.789				
% RSD			1.38				

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of six different sample solutions should not more than 2
- The %RSD obtained is within the limit, hence the method is rugged.

ACCURACY:**The accuracy results for Levofloxacin**

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (ppm)	Amount Found (ppm)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	308408	60	60	100%	100%
100%	600619	120	120	100%	
150%	894293	180	180	100%	

The accuracy results for Moxifloxacin

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (ppm)	Amount Found (ppm)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	216092	1.5	1.52	101.3	99.7%
100%	423626	3	2.9	99.3	
150%	634469.7	4.5	4.48	98.6	

Acceptance Criteria:

- The percentage recovery was found to be within the limit (98-102%).

The results obtained for recovery at 50%, 100%, 150% are within the limits. Hence method is accurate.

Table:7.19 Results for Robustness**Levofloxacin:**

Parameter used for sample analysis	Peak Area	Retention Time	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor
Actual Flow rate of 1.0 mL/min	600122	2.456	5215	1.8
Less Flow rate of 0.9 mL/min	651206	2.741	5199	1.79
More Flow rate of 1.1 mL/min	546820	2.270	5234	1.8
Less organic phase	586420	3.266	5298	1.8
More organic phase	542813	2.147	5287	1.76

Acceptance criteria:

The tailing factor should be less than 2.0 and the number of theoretical plates (N) should be more than 2000.

Table:7.20 Results for Robustness**Moxifloxacin:**

Parameter used for sample analysis	Peak Area	Retention Time	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor
Actual Flow rate of 1.0 mL/min	422042	4.312	5648	1.5
Less Flow rate of 0.9 mL/min	453012	4.830	5687	1.6
More Flow rate of 1.1 mL/min	398654	3.979	5602	1.5
Less organic phase	445983	3.266	5643	1.55

More organic phase	402315	2.147	5699	1.51
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Acceptance criteria:

The tailing factor should be less than 2.0 and the number of theoretical plates (N) should be more than 2000.

8. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:**Summary:**

This study focuses on the development and validation of a robust, accurate, and reproducible reverse-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method for the simultaneous estimation of moxifloxacin and levofloxacin in bulk drugs and pharmaceutical dosage forms. The separation was efficiently achieved using a Symmetry ODS C18 column (4.6mm × 150mm, 5µm particle size) with a mobile phase of Methanol: Water (64:36% v/v).

The method employed a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min, with the column maintained at 38°C. Detection was carried out at a wavelength of 220 nm using a Waters Alliance 2695 HPLC system with a PDA Detector (996 model). The injection volume was 20 µl, and the total run time was 7.0 minutes.

CONCLUSION:

The developed RP-HPLC method is simple, rapid, and highly sensitive for the simultaneous determination of moxifloxacin and levofloxacin in both bulk and pharmaceutical formulations. The method is validated in accordance with ICH guidelines and is suitable for routine quality control analysis. The use of a PDA detector and optimized chromatographic conditions ensures specificity and reliable quantification of both analytes without interference from excipients or other formulation components.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The Authors are thankful to the Management and Principal, Sri Indu Institute of Pharmacy, Sheriguda (V), Ibrahimpatnam, Telangana, for extending support to carry out the research work. Finally, the authors express their gratitude to the Sura Pharma Labs, Dilsukhnagar, Hyderabad, for providing research equipment and facilities.

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